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Family Dynamics and Social Adjustment of Secondary School Students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between family dynamics and the social adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study investigated the relationship between family cohesion, family communication, parenting style, and social adjustment of students. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study consisted of 8,065 secondary school students, while a sample of 667 SS II students was selected using the proportionate stratified random sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Family Dynamics and Social Adjustment Questionnaire (FDSAQ)”. The instrument was validated by experts in guidance and counseling and measurement and evaluation, and its internal consistency reliability was established using the Cronbach alpha method, which yielded an overall coefficient of 0.80. Data collected were analyzed

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using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics to answer the research questions and test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that family cohesion and family communication have strong positive relationships with social adjustment, while parenting style has a very strong positive relationship with social adjustment of secondary school students. All the relationships were found to be statistically significant. Based on these findings, the study concluded that family dynamics play a significant role in enhancing the social adjustment of secondary school students. It was recommended among others that parents should maintain strong emotional bonds, practice effective communication, and adopt appropriate parenting styles to enhance students' social adjustment.

Keywords: family dynamics, family cohesion, family communication, parenting style, social adjustment

Introduction

Secondary school students are constantly engaged in interactions with peers, teachers, and family members, and these interactions can significantly influence their behavioral patterns and overall adjustment in society. At this stage of development, adolescents are particularly sensitive to social influences, as they strive to form their identity, gain acceptance, and establish meaningful relationships. The school environment, which brings together individuals from diverse backgrounds, presents both opportunities and challenges for social development. As a result, students must learn to handle various social situations, manage interpersonal relationships, and respond appropriately to social expectations.

Social adjustment is therefore a critical aspect of students' development, as it determines how well they are able to adapt to their social environment, form relationships, and function effectively within and outside the school setting. According to Onyechefule and Ukaegbu (2025), social adjustment refers to the ability of an individual to adapt to social demands, establish healthy interpersonal relationships, and behave in a socially acceptable manner. It involves the ability to cope with social demands, adjust to new situations, and maintain a balance between personal needs and societal expectations. Students who possess good social adjustment may demonstrate positive behaviors such as cooperation, respect for others, emotional stability, and effective communication. On the

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other hand, poor social adjustment can manifest in behaviors such as aggression, withdrawal, loneliness, and difficulty in forming or maintaining relationships.

One major factor that may influence students' social adjustment is family dynamics. Family dynamics is an important concept in understanding students' behavior and adjustment patterns, especially during adolescence when individuals are highly influenced by their immediate environment. In the context of this study, "family dynamics" refers to the patterns of interaction, communication, roles, relationships, and emotional connections among members of a family. According to Ekechukwu (2020), family dynamics include parenting styles, family cohesion, communication patterns, emotional support, and disciplinary practices within the home. However, for the purpose of this study, only family cohesion, family communication, and parenting style were studied.

Family cohesion refers to the emotional bonding and closeness among family members as highlighted by Egbule and Chimaobi (2021). It reflects the degree to which family members are connected, supportive, and involved in one another's lives. In cohesive families, there is a strong sense of unity, love, and mutual respect, which creates a stable and nurturing environment for children's development. Students from such families may develop a sense of belonging, emotional security, and positive social behaviors, as they feel valued and supported within the home. This emotional stability can translate into confidence in social settings, enabling them to interact effectively with peers and teachers. Conversely, low family cohesion, characterized by weak emotional ties, lack of support, and limited interaction among family members, may result in feelings of isolation, insecurity, and neglect. Such conditions can negatively affect students' social adjustment, as they may struggle to trust others, form relationships, or cope with social challenges.

According to Ogunleye (2023), family communication refers to the exchange of information, feelings, and ideas among family members. It is a vital component of family dynamics that shapes how individuals understand themselves and relate to others. Effective communication within the family can foster understanding, trust, and emotional stability, which are essential for positive social interaction among students. When family members communicate openly and respectfully, children learn important social skills such as listening, expressing themselves clearly, and resolving conflicts peacefully. These skills can be transferred to the school environment, where students are required to interact with others regularly. On the other hand, poor communication patterns, such as frequent misunderstandings, lack of openness, or harsh communication, may hinder the

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development of these essential social skills. Students from such environments may exhibit difficulties in expressing their thoughts, managing emotions, and maintaining healthy relationships, thereby affecting their overall social adjustment.

Parenting style refers to the consistent patterns of behavior, attitudes, and strategies that parents use in raising and interacting with their children (Ukaegbu & Edem, 2021). It encompasses the ways in which parents provide guidance, discipline, support, and supervision within the family setting. According to Baumrind (1991), cited in Ukaegbu and Edem (2021), parenting styles such as authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and neglectful styles can significantly influence children's behavior. Students raised in supportive and responsive family environments tend to exhibit better social skills and adaptability compared to those raised in harsh or inconsistent environments.

From the foregoing, therefore, family dynamics appear to play a vital role in shaping students' social adjustment. However, variations in family structures and interaction patterns may result in differences in students' adjustment outcomes. Therefore, there is a need to investigate how specific components of family dynamics relate to social adjustment among secondary school students in specific contexts. It is against this background that this study investigated the relationship between family dynamics (family cohesion, family communication, and parenting style) and social adjustment of secondary school students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Social adjustment of secondary school students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State has increasingly become a matter of concern, as it plays a vital role in determining how effectively students relate with others and adapt to their social environment. Many students appear to experience challenges in developing appropriate social skills needed for meaningful interaction within the school and the larger society. These challenges are often reflected in behaviors such as aggression, poor communication, social withdrawal, lack of cooperation, and difficulty in forming or maintaining relationships. Such maladjusted behaviors may not only disrupt the school environment but also hinder students' academic progress and overall social well-being.

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One major factor that may influence students' social adjustment is the nature of their family environment. Many students may be exposed to unstable or ineffective family settings characterized by poor communication, weak emotional bonds, and inconsistent parenting practices. Such family conditions may limit students' opportunities to develop essential social skills such as cooperation, empathy, and effective communication, which are necessary for proper adjustment. Consequently, students from such backgrounds may find it difficult to relate positively with others or adapt to social expectations within the school environment.

Although previous studies have investigated the influence of the family on child development, there is limited empirical evidence specifically addressing how key components of family dynamics such as family cohesion, family communication, and parenting style relate to the social adjustment of secondary school students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State. This gap in knowledge underscores the need to investigate the relationship between family dynamics and social adjustment of secondary school students in the study area.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between family dynamics and social adjustment of secondary school students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. In specific terms, the study sought to determine the following:

- i. The relationship between family cohesion and social adjustment of secondary school students.
- ii. The relationship between family communication and social adjustment of secondary school students.
- iii. The relationship between parenting style and social adjustment of secondary school students.

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Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What is the relationship between family cohesion and social adjustment of secondary school students?
- ii. What is the relationship between family communication and social adjustment of secondary school students?
- iii. What is the relationship between parenting style and social adjustment of secondary school students?

Null Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- i. There is no significant relationship between family cohesion and social adjustment of secondary school students.
- ii. There is no significant relationship between family communication and social adjustment of secondary school students.
- iii. There is no significant relationship between parenting style and social adjustment of secondary school students.

Significance of the Study

The findings of this study will be beneficial to students, parents, teachers, counselors, educational policymakers, and researchers. Students will benefit from the findings of the study by gaining awareness of how family interactions influence their social behavior and adjustment patterns.

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Parents will benefit from the findings of the study by understanding the importance of maintaining positive family relationships, effective communication, and supportive parenting practices to enhance their children's social development. Teachers will find the outcome of this study useful in understanding the background factors influencing students' behavior, which will help them adopt appropriate strategies for managing students in the classroom. School counselors will benefit from the findings of the study by using the findings to design intervention programs aimed at improving students' social adjustment through family-based counseling approaches.

Educational policymakers will also benefit from the findings of the study by formulating policies and programs that promote family involvement in students' development. Finally, the study will contribute to existing literature and serve as a reference material for future researchers who may wish to conduct further studies on family dynamics and social adjustment.

Scope of the Study

The study focused on the relationship between family dynamics and social adjustment of secondary school students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State. Components of family dynamics, namely family cohesion, family communication, and parenting style, served as the independent variables, while social adjustment served as the dependent variable. The study was delimited to senior secondary II students in public schools in the Uyo and Nsit Ubium local government areas of Akwa Ibom State.

Theoretical Framework

Family Systems Theory by Murray Bowen (1978)

Murray Bowen propounded the Family Systems Theory in 1978. The theory focuses on the family as an interconnected emotional unit in which the behavior of each member is influenced by the interactions, roles, and relationships within the family system. The theory posits that individuals cannot be fully understood in isolation, as their behaviors and attitudes are shaped by patterns of family interaction such as communication, cohesion, and parenting practices. According to Bowen, the stability or instability of a family system significantly affects the emotional and social development of its members, particularly children and adolescents.

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The theory emphasizes key aspects of family dynamics such as emotional bonding (family cohesion), communication patterns, and parenting style. Family cohesion promotes a sense of belonging and security, which enhances positive behavioral outcomes among children.

Effective family communication fosters understanding, trust, and emotional expression, while appropriate parenting styles provide guidance, discipline, and support necessary for proper development. Conversely, dysfunctional family systems characterized by poor communication, weak emotional bonds, and inconsistent parenting may lead to behavioral and emotional challenges among children. Furthermore, Family Systems Theory explains that children develop behavioral patterns based on the stability and functionality of their family environment. A well-functioning family system encourages positive social behaviors such as cooperation, respect, and effective interaction, while a poorly functioning system may result in maladaptive behaviors such as aggression, withdrawal, and poor interpersonal relationships. Thus, the theory highlights the importance of family dynamics in shaping the social and emotional outcomes of individuals.

The relevance of family systems theory to the present study lies in the fact that secondary school students are products of their family environments, and their behaviors in school are often reflections of the interactions and experiences within the family. Family dynamics variables such as family cohesion, family communication, and parenting style play a significant role in determining how students relate to others and adjust socially. Students from stable and supportive family systems may exhibit positive social behaviors and better adjustment, while those from dysfunctional family systems may experience difficulties in social interaction. Therefore, family systems theory provides a suitable framework for understanding the relationship between family dynamics and social adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo and Nsit Ubium local government areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Social Learning Theory by Albert Bandura (1977)

The Social Learning Theory was propounded by Albert Bandura in 1977. The theory emphasizes that behavior is learned through observation, imitation, and interaction with others within the social environment. According to Bandura, individuals, especially children and adolescents, acquire new behaviors by observing significant others such as parents, peers, and teachers and by modeling their actions. The theory posits that learning

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occurs through processes such as attention, retention, reproduction, and motivation, which enable individuals to internalize and replicate observed behaviors. The theory further explains that social behaviors are shaped by reinforcement and consequences. When individuals observe behaviors that are rewarded, they are more likely to imitate such behaviors, while behaviors that are punished are less likely to be repeated.

Social Learning Theory also highlights that positive social behaviors such as cooperation, empathy, communication, and conflict resolution can be learned through exposure to appropriate role models. Conversely, exposure to negative behaviors such as aggression, poor communication, or antisocial conduct may lead to maladjustment. Therefore, the social environment plays a crucial role in shaping how individuals adapt to social expectations and interact with others.

The relevance of social learning theory to the present study lies in its explanation of how students develop social adjustment skills. Secondary school students observe and learn behaviors from their family members, particularly through family interactions such as communication patterns and parenting styles. Students who are exposed to positive family dynamics are more likely to develop appropriate social skills and adjust effectively within the school environment. On the other hand, students exposed to negative family behaviors may exhibit poor social adjustment. Therefore, social learning theory provides a suitable framework for understanding how family dynamics influence the social adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo and Nsit Ubium local government areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Empirical Literature

Okafor and Nwankwo (2020) conducted a study on family cohesion and social adjustment among secondary school students in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population consisted of 1,240 students, from which a sample of 310 students was selected using the stratified random sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a structured questionnaire titled “Family Cohesion and Social Adjustment Scale (FCSAS)”. The instrument was validated by experts in Guidance and Counselling and Measurement and Evaluation, while a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The findings revealed that family cohesion has a significant positive relationship with social adjustment among students. Based on the findings, it was

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recommended that parents should strengthen emotional bonding within the family to enhance students' social development. Bello (2021) investigated the influence of family cohesion on adolescents' social adjustment in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of 980 secondary school students, while a sample of 245 students was selected using a simple random sampling technique. Data were collected using a researcher-developed questionnaire titled "Family Influence and Social Adjustment Questionnaire (FISAQ)". The instrument was validated and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.76. Data were analyzed using regression analysis. The findings indicated that family cohesion alone does not significantly predict social adjustment unless combined with other factors such as communication and parental involvement.

Olatunji and Adewale (2019) carried out a study on family communication and social behavior of adolescents in Oyo State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population consisted of 1,500 secondary school students, with a sample of 375 students selected using a multistage sampling technique. The instrument for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Family Communication and Social Behavior Scale (FCSBS)". The instrument was validated by experts and had a reliability coefficient of 0.80. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The findings revealed that family communication significantly influences students' social behavior and adjustment. Brown (2021) examined the role of communication in adolescents' social adjustment in selected high schools in the United States. The study used a descriptive survey design. The population comprised 1,200 students, from which a sample of 300 students was selected using a random sampling technique. Data were collected using a standardized questionnaire titled "Adolescent Communication and Adjustment Inventory (ACAI)". The instrument was validated and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.78. Data were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The findings showed that communication alone does not significantly predict social adjustment unless supported by emotional bonding and parental guidance.

Nwoye and Okonkwo (2020) conducted a study on parenting style and social competence among secondary school students in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population consisted of 1,350 students, while a sample of 338 students was selected using the stratified random sampling technique. The instrument used was a questionnaire titled "Parenting Style and Social Competence Scale (PSCS)". The instrument was validated and had a reliability coefficient of 0.84 using

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Cronbach's alpha. Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The findings revealed that parenting style significantly influences students' social competence and adjustment. Eze (2023) investigated the influence of peer and parental factors on social adjustment of secondary school students in Imo State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey design. The population consisted of 1,100 students, from which a sample of 275 students was selected using a simple random sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled "Social Adjustment Determinants Questionnaire (SADQ)". The instrument was validated and yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.79. Data were analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The findings indicated that peer influence has a stronger effect on students' social adjustment than parenting style in some contexts.

Design of the Study

A correlational research design was adopted for the study. According to Nworgu (2015), a correlational research design is used to establish relationships among variables as they naturally occur without manipulation. Thus, this design is suitable for investigating how family dynamics relate to the social adjustment of secondary school students in the Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 8,065 secondary school students in public secondary schools in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The students were distributed across public secondary schools in the study area (Akwa Ibom State Secondary Schools Board, 2026).

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for the study consisted of 675 secondary school students drawn from a population of 2,184 students in public secondary schools in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane's formula for finite populations.. A proportionate stratified random sampling technique was adopted in selecting the respondents. The population was first stratified based on the two local government areas, after which the sample was proportionately

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distributed according to the size of each stratum. Thereafter, a simple random sampling technique was used to select the respondents from the respective schools.

Instrumentation

The instrument used for data collection in this study was a structured questionnaire titled “Family Dynamics and Social Adjustment Questionnaire (FDSAQ)” developed by the researchers. The questionnaire was divided into two sections, namely Section A and Section B. Section A consisted of 15 items, with five items designed to measure each of the independent sub-variables of family dynamics (family cohesion, family communication, and parenting style), while Section B consisted of 15 items that measured social adjustment. The items were structured on a four-point format of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD), weighted 4, 3, 2, and 1, respectively.

Validation of the Instrument

The instrument was subjected to face validation by three experts, comprising two experts in Guidance and Counselling and one expert in Measurement and Evaluation, Department of Psychological Foundations of Education, all from the Faculty of Education. The experts examined the instrument for clarity, relevance, appropriateness of language, and adequacy in measuring the variables under study. Their corrections and suggestions were incorporated into the final version of the instrument to ensure that it adequately measured family dynamics and social adjustment of secondary school students.

Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the instrument was established using the internal consistency method. The instrument was administered to 30 secondary school students who were part of the population of the study but not sampled for the study. The data obtained were analyzed using the Cronbach Alpha statistic. The reliability coefficients obtained were 0.80 for family cohesion, 0.78 for family communication, 0.79 for parenting style, and 0.82 for social adjustment, with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.80. With these values, the use of the instrument for the study was justified.

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Method of Data Collection

The researchers used a direct administration method in collecting data for the study. Permission was obtained from the sampled school principals before administering the questionnaire. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed to the respondents in their respective schools. The purpose of the study was explained to the students, and they were assured of confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. The respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, after which the completed copies were collected immediately. Out of the 675 copies of the questionnaire distributed, 667 were correctly completed and returned, while 8 copies were not returned by the respondents. The 667 returned copies were used for the analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) statistics. The correlation coefficients (r-values) were used to answer all the research questions by determining the strength and direction of the relationship between family dynamics variables and social adjustment. The null hypotheses were tested using the associated p-values of the correlation coefficients at the 0.05 level of significance. All data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Decision Rule

For the research questions, the value of Pearson's r was interpreted as follows:

±0.10 - ±0.39 Weak relationship

±0.40 - ±0.59 Moderate relationship

±0.60 - ±0.79 Strong relationship

±0.80 - ±1.00 Very strong relationship

Furthermore, if the value of significance is less than the 0.05 alpha level of significance, the null hypothesis of no significance was rejected while the alternate hypothesis was upheld and vice versa.

Results

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient of the relationship between family cohesion and social adjustment of secondary school students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State (n = 667)

Variables	n	r	p-value	Remark
Family Cohesion	667	0.73	.001	Strong positive relationship; Significant.
Social Adjustment	667			

The result presented in Table 1 reveals a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.73, indicating a strong positive relationship between family cohesion and social adjustment. This implies that as the level of family cohesion increases, the level of social adjustment among students also increases. Furthermore, the p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between family cohesion and social adjustment is rejected.

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient of the relationship between family communication and social adjustment of secondary school students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State (n = 667)

Variables	n	r	p-value	Remark
Family Communication	667	0.73	.001	Strong positive relationship; Significant.
Social Adjustment	667			

The result presented in Table 2 reveals a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.73, indicating a strong positive relationship between family communication and social adjustment. This implies that as the level of effective communication within the family increases, the level of social adjustment among students also increases. Furthermore, the p-value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between family communication and social adjustment is rejected.

Table 3: Pearson Product Moment Correlation coefficient of the relationship between parenting style and social adjustment of secondary school students in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State (n = 667)

Variables	n	r	p-value	Remark
Parenting Style	667	0.82	.000	Very Strong positive relationship; Significant.
Social Adjustment	667			

The result presented in Table 3 reveals a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.82, indicating a very strong positive relationship between parenting style and social adjustment. This implies that appropriate and effective parenting styles are associated with higher levels of social adjustment among students. Furthermore, the p-value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that the relationship is statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no significant relationship between parenting style and social adjustment is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The analysis of data on the relationship between family cohesion and social adjustment of secondary school students revealed that family cohesion has a strong positive relationship with social adjustment. In addition, the test of the corresponding null hypothesis showed that family cohesion significantly relates to social adjustment, suggesting that the level of emotional bonding and closeness within the family plays a crucial role in shaping students' ability to adjust socially. Family cohesion provides a supportive and secure environment that fosters confidence, trust, and positive interpersonal behaviors among students. Students from cohesive families are more likely to interact effectively with peers and teachers, exhibit cooperation, and maintain healthy relationships. This finding is consistent with the study of Okafor and Nwankwo (2020), who found that strong family bonding enhances adolescents' social competence and adjustment. However, this finding contrasts with the work of Bello (2021), who reported that family cohesion alone may not significantly influence social adjustment without the support of effective communication and parental guidance.

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The analysis of data on the relationship between family communication and social adjustment of secondary school students showed that family communication has a strong positive relationship with social adjustment. Additionally, the test of the corresponding null hypothesis indicated that family communication significantly relates to social adjustment, suggesting that effective communication within the family is essential in promoting students' social adjustment. Family communication enables students to learn how to express themselves, listen to others, and resolve interpersonal issues constructively. These communication skills are critical for building relationships and functioning effectively in social settings such as the school environment. Students who experience open and supportive communication at home are more likely to demonstrate confidence, tolerance, and positive interaction with others. In the context of secondary school students in the study area, family communication serves as a major factor in enhancing social adjustment. This finding agrees with Olatunji and Adewale (2019), who found that effective family communication significantly improves adolescents' social behavior and adjustment. However, this finding disagrees with the study of Brown (2021), who argued that communication alone may not guarantee social adjustment without emotional bonding and proper parental control.

The analysis of data on the relationship between parenting style and social adjustment of secondary school students indicated that parenting style has a very strong positive relationship with social adjustment. More so, the test of the corresponding null hypothesis showed that parenting style significantly relates to social adjustment, suggesting that the manner in which parents raise and interact with their children plays a highly significant role in shaping students' social behavior and adjustment patterns. Parenting styles such as authoritative parenting, which combines warmth with appropriate control, tend to promote independence, responsibility, and positive social behaviors among students. On the other hand, negative parenting styles such as authoritarian or neglectful approaches may hinder the development of social skills and lead to maladjustment. Students exposed to effective parenting are more likely to exhibit cooperation, respect, and the ability to interact positively with others. In the context of the study area, parenting style appears to be a dominant factor influencing students' social adjustment. This finding is in line with the study of Nwoye and Okonkwo (2020), who found that parenting practices significantly influence adolescents' social competence and adjustment. However, this

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finding contrasts with the work of Eze (2023), who reported that peer influence may have a stronger effect on students' social adjustment than parenting style in certain contexts.

Conclusion

The study concluded that family dynamics components such as family cohesion, family communication, and parenting style play significant roles in enhancing social adjustment among secondary school students. Students who come from families characterized by strong emotional bonding, effective communication, and appropriate parenting practices are more likely to exhibit positive social behaviors, while poor family dynamics may hinder students' ability to adjust socially.

Implications for Counselling

The findings of this study have important implications for counseling practice. School counselors need to recognize that students' social adjustment is strongly influenced by their family background and interactions. Therefore, counseling services should not only focus on students but also involve family-oriented approaches. Counselors should design intervention programs that promote positive family relationships, effective communication, and appropriate parenting practices.

Furthermore, counselors should provide guidance and support to students who exhibit poor social adjustment by helping them develop essential social skills such as communication, cooperation, and conflict resolution. Counselors can also organize parent education programs and workshops to sensitize parents to the importance of maintaining cohesive family environments and adopting effective parenting styles. Additionally, group counseling sessions may be used to help students share experiences, build confidence, and improve their interpersonal relationships.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

- i. Parents in Uyo and Nsit Ubium Local Government Areas should be encouraged to promote family cohesion by maintaining close emotional bonds and supportive relationships with their children to enhance their social adjustment.

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- ii. Families should be sensitized to the importance of effective communication through seminars and community programs to help students develop better interpersonal and communication skills.
- iii. Counselors and educational stakeholders should organize parent education programs to guide parents on adopting appropriate parenting styles that foster positive social behaviors among students.

References

- Bello, A. S. (2021). Influence of family cohesion on adolescents' social adjustment in Kwara State. *Nigerian Journal of Guidance and Counselling*, 15(1), 78–90.
- Brown, J. M. (2021). Communication and adolescent social adjustment in high school settings. *Journal of Adolescent Research*, 36(4), 512–528.
- Egbule, J. F., & Chimaobi, K. C. (2021). Family cohesion and emotional development of adolescents in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Guidance and Counselling Studies*, 14(2), 33–47.
- Ekechukwu, R. N. (2020). Family dynamics and adolescent behavioural outcomes in South- East Nigeria. *African Journal of Social and Behavioural Sciences*, 10(1), 56–68.
- Eze, U. C. (2023). Peer and parental influences on social adjustment of secondary school students in Imo State. *International Journal of Educational Studies*, 18(1), 89–101.
- Nworgu, B. G. (2015). *Educational research: Basic issues and methodology* (3rd ed.). University Trust Publishers.

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- Nwoye, M. N., & Okonkwo, E. C. (2020). Parenting style and social competence among secondary school students in Anambra State. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 14(2), 66–79.
- Ogunleye, A. A. (2023). Family communication patterns and social competence among adolescents in South-West Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Educational Research and Development*, 22(1), 75–89.
- Okafor, C. N., & Nwankwo, I. O. (2020). Family cohesion and social adjustment among secondary school students in Enugu State, Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Psychology and Development*, 12(2), 45–58.
- Olatunji, T. A., & Adewale, R. O. (2019). Family communication and social behaviour of adolescents in Oyo State. *Journal of Social Sciences and Education*, 11(3), 102–114.
- Onyechefule, C. N., & Ukaegbu, A. W. (2025). Social adjustment and interpersonal behaviour among secondary school students in Nigeria. *Journal of Educational Psychology and Behavioural Studies*, 18(2), 112–125.
- Ukaegbu, A. W., & Edem, M. E. (2021). Parenting styles and behavioural adjustment among secondary school students in Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Social Science Research*, 9(3), 101–115.

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FAMILY DYNAMICS AND SOCIAL ADJUSTMENT QUESTIONNAIRE (FDSAQ)

Instruction: Choose your response from the number of alternatives by ticking appropriately in the box provided.

Keys: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD)

Section A: Family Dynamics

S/N	Family Cohesion	SA	A	D	SD
1	My family members spend quality time together regularly.				
2	There is a strong sense of unity among members of my family.				
3	My family members support one another during difficult times.				
4	I feel a sense of belonging in my family.				
5	My family members show concern for each other's well-being.				
	Family Communication				
6	My family members communicate openly with one another.				
7	My parents listen to me when I speak.				
8	My parents encourage me to share my opinions.				
9	Conflicts in my family are resolved through discussion.				
10	I feel comfortable talking to my parents about my problems.				
	Parenting Style				
11	My parents set clear rules for me to follow.				
12	My parents explain the reasons for their decisions.				
13	My parents encourage me to be independent.				
14	My parents discipline me when I do something wrong.				
15	My parents guide me in making good decisions.				

Section B: Social Adjustment

S/N	Items	SA	A	D	SD
1	I find it easy to make friends in school.				
2	I relate well with my classmates.				
3	I feel comfortable interacting with my teachers.				
4	I participate actively in class discussions.				

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5	I feel accepted by my classmates.				
6	I communicate effectively with my classmates in school.				
7	I am able to work well in a team.				
8	I respect school rules.				
9	I maintain good relationships with my classmates.				
10	I am able to adapt to different school situations.				
11	I feel a sense of belonging in my school.				
12	I respect the feelings of my classmates.				
13	I participate actively in group assignments.				
14	I avoid isolating myself from others in school.				
15	I interact freely with students from different classes.				